

Kamu Yararı Açısından Yenilenebilir Enerji Yönetimi

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Özet

Kamu yönetimi açısından enerji konusu, küresel ölçekte stratejik öncelik olmayı sürdürmektedir. Özellikle Avrupa ülkeleri, enerji arz güvenliğini sağlamak amacıyla yenilenebilir enerji kaynaklarının kapasitesini artırmaya yönelik düzenlemeler geliştirmiştir. Bu süreçte yenilenebilir enerji kavramı, yalnızca iklim politikalarıyla sınırlı kalmayıp, siyasi istikrar ve güvenlik politikasıyla ilişkilendirilerek yeniden tanımlanmıştır. Bu çalışmanın temel araştırma sorusu, yenilenebilir enerjinin kamu yararını hangi yönlerden nasıl etkilediğidir. Yenilenebilir enerji kullanımı, sera gazı emisyonlarını azaltarak su ve hava kalitesini iyileştirmekte; böylece ekolojik dengeyi koruyarak iklim değişikliğiyle mücadelede rol oynamaktadır. Bu yönüyle çevresel sürdürülebilirliği teşvik eden yenilenebilir enerji yatırımı, ekonomik kazanımla uzun vadeli sosyal ve ekolojik fayda sağlayıp kamu yararına hizmet etmektedir. Kamu yararının somut-çıktı üzerinden değerlendirildiği göz önüne alındığında, yenilenebilir enerji yönetimi bu yararı doğrudan görünür kılmaktadır. Kamu otoritesi kararı doğrultusunda yapılan yenilenebilir enerji yatırımı, anayasal temele dayanan siyasal ve toplumsal ilkeler çerçevesinde kamu yararı kapsamında değerlendirilmektedir. Yenilenebilir enerjinin toplumsal yararı konusuna değinen bu çalışmada, literatür incelemesi yapılmıştır. Uygulamada vaka analizi yöntemi kullanılmıştır. Kamu yararı kavramı teorik çerçevede ele alınmış; yenilenebilir enerji politikalarına yönelik uluslararası örnekler incelenmiş, Türkiye özelinde düzenleyici mekanizma ve kalkınma planları değerlendirilmiş, kamu yönetimi bağlamında yerel yönetimler için öneriler sunulmuştur.

Anahtar Kelimeler:

Kamu Yararı,
Toplumsal Fayda,
Yenilenebilir Enerji
Yönetim

Governance Of Renewable Energy in Terms of Public Interest

Abstract

Public Interest,
Community
Benefit,
Renewable
Energy,
Governance

In terms of public governance, energy remains a strategic priority on a global scale. Particularly in European countries, regulations have been developed to increase the capacity of renewable energy sources in order to ensure energy supply security. In this process, the concept of renewable energy has been redefined—not merely as part of climate policy, but also in relation to political stability and security policy. The central research question of this study is: In what ways and to what extent does renewable energy affect the public interest? The use of renewable energy helps reduce greenhouse gas emissions, improves water and air quality, and thereby contributes to ecological balance and the fight against climate change. From this perspective, renewable energy investments promote environmental sustainability and generate long-term social and ecological benefits alongside economic gains, thus serving the public interest. Considering that public interest is often evaluated through tangible outcomes, renewable energy governance makes this benefit visibly measurable. Investments made under the authority of public institutions are assessed within the framework of constitutional, political, and societal principles as part of the public interest. This study, which addresses the societal benefits of renewable energy, includes a literature review. In the empirical section, a case study method is employed. The concept of public interest is examined within a theoretical framework; international examples of renewable energy policies are analyzed; regulatory mechanisms and development plans specific to Türkiye are evaluated; and recommendations are offered for local governments within the context of public governance.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the context of public administration and the future of societies, the debate on sustainability is intensifying. As UN Secretary-General Antonio Guterres has emphasized, a well-managed transition towards a future dominated by renewable energy can have beneficial outcomes for humanity, such as improving access to energy, combating climate change and protecting public health by improving air quality. Renewable energy sources such as hydrogen, solar, and wind help prevent the depletion of natural resources and minimize environmental impact. Renewable energy has the potential to meet two-thirds of global energy demand and, by 2050, contribute to reducing greenhouse gas emissions, thereby supporting the goal of keeping the average surface temperature increase below 2°C (Gielen et al., 2019).

Public acceptance of renewable energy is considerably high (Gavin, 2019). Research has shown that regardless of age, education level, or political orientation, people tend to support the use of renewable energy sources. One study revealed that in 13 countries, the majority of 26,000 respondents favored a future fully powered by renewable energy (Gavin, 2019; Orsted, 2017). This interaction, when viewed through the lens of residential dynamics, reflects the role of cities. Although cities occupy only 3% of the Earth's surface, they account for 75% of carbon emissions and 70% of global energy consumption (Savcı & Atmaca, 2022). As income levels rise among urban residents, electricity consumption also increases. Transitioning cities to renewable energy can purify air and water, reduce health problems, and lower carbon levels that contribute to the climate crisis (Osei-Kusi et al., 2024). Such positive outcomes align with the definition of public interest, which refers to benefits aimed at enhancing the overall welfare of individuals and society. The primary goal of public interest is to improve the quality of life for both individuals and communities. In this context, the concept of the common good or collective benefit can be considered closely related to public interest. Renewable energy and public interest should be recognized as interconnected and mutually reinforcing domains. As concerns over climate change, environmental degradation, and energy security grow, investments in renewable energy solutions are increasing. These investments provide environmental benefits for humanity and serve the public interest (Demir, 2022). Electricity generation based on renewable energy sources plays a significant role in ensuring energy supply security and promoting environmental sustainability. Compared to fossil fuels, the environmental impacts of these sources are generally lower and considered acceptable. In Turkey, under Law No. 5346, the Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources has been assigned the responsibility of identifying and developing renewable energy resource areas (Süslü, 2024).

The study first addresses the concept of public interest. Subsequently, examples from various countries in the field of renewable energy are examined, followed by a review of regulations and development plans related to renewable energy in Türkiye. Finally, regulatory recommendations concerning renewable energy are presented from the perspective of public administration.

2. USE OF RENEWABLE ENERGY: SERVING PUBLIC INTEREST

The aim of the study is to highlight the correlation between public interest and renewable energy, and to emphasize that while “caution towards the new” remains valid, transitioning to a beneficial model can be advanced to some extent. In this context, the interaction between renewable energy and public interest can be examined. The main research question of the study is: In what ways and how does renewable energy affect public interest?

The impact of renewable energy on public interest is examined in the context of various country examples, while Turkey's position in this field is evaluated through a case study approach. During the data collection process, a literature review method was applied using both primary and secondary sources. The literature review includes the analysis of articles and reports prepared by national and international institutions and organizations. Although there is a substantial body of international literature on the relationship between public interest and renewable energy, it remains a relatively underexplored topic in Turkish public administration literature; therefore, this study focuses on that gap.

The concept of “public interest” may evoke, in the collective memory, associations with “expropriation,” where individual rights can be easily restricted in favor of societal benefit. In this study, however, “public interest” will be considered in terms of the benefits that increased use of renewable energy can provide to all humanity—such as the right to live in a clean environment, and access to clean water and air. In pursuit of this aim, data and examples are referenced. Public administration may be required to analyze data that spans various correlations

and scientific disciplines. At first glance, is this merely a “technical-engineering issue”? (Indeed, technical reports also contribute to societal benefit by adhering to quality and standards.) While it may be perceived this way, the topic of energy—when considered from administrative, social, and economic dimensions—reflects a subject that has not been sufficiently processed or debated in terms of producing information that the public can access, analyze, interpret, and evaluate. If energy can be brought to the agenda and prioritized through its dimensions of public interest, social-environmental benefit, and contribution to humanity, then the purpose of such studies may be fulfilled.

2.1. Perspectives on Public Interest

Although the concept is difficult to define, a perspective can be offered. In its seemingly simple and straightforward explanation, the unlimited supply of clean and green energy may represent an ideal win-win situation: positive aspects such as carbon emission control, securing resources, and ensuring continuous supply. However, opposition may arise from groups prioritizing their own interests over national or international good—such as the “Not in My Backyard” (NIMBY) preference. In Europe, some protests are reported to stem from issues of effective participation in renewable energy planning. In general, about two-thirds of society tends to favor renewable sources (Hagget, C. 2009: 297). Since the 1970s, public trust in government has been declining in developed countries. Within the framework of constitutional law, scientific data, public knowledge, and public trust (Cunningham-Burley, 2006), issues such as ecosystem integrity, environmental law, sustainability, the merit of a broad public interest mosaic, interest groups, and the debate between narrow versus broad public interest (Treves et al., 2017) come into play. Public trust in science benefits the public interest, and the reciprocal relationship—how much science needs the public—can be discussed (Goldenberg, 2023). Trust in a country (e.g., the United States) may emerge through dimensions such as popular culture, technology, and universities (Bok 1992). Since the public is not a single entity, questions arise: which public (general, specific community or group), what expectations does the public have from science, how do rules or policies guarantee meeting these expectations, and how important is it to meet them (Resnik, 2011)? These questions offer insights to support public policy. Through individual, semi-social, and societal approaches, solutions to harmful public distrust can be sought. Issues such as the over-idealization of science and the overburdening of citizens may be addressed through a holistic societal approach, considering acceptance, transition dynamics, public reception of scientific knowledge, and the positive or negative impact of social forces on trustworthiness (Contessa, 2023). On the other hand, although public trust is not directly correlated with e-government service delivery, it has been found to be related to investment support for e-government. More frequent internet users are more likely to trust e-government services (Horsburgh et al. 2011).

Establishing and maintaining public trust may require addressing complex and conflicting questions. Wind and solar energy projects, which affect large areas of both public and private land, may lead those who agree or disagree to focus on the doctrine of public trust and refine their objectives accordingly. There is a segment of society that views the use of public lands and large private areas for renewable energy development—due to environmental and climate change benefits—as compatible with both public interest and the public trust doctrine. On the other hand, opponents argue that the intensive land use, potential adverse effects on endangered species, open spaces, aesthetic values, and untouched natural landscapes contradict the principles of the public trust doctrine. The question arises: how should the balance between benefit and harm be achieved? It is proposed that renewable energy development be built in alignment with the public trust doctrine, without compromising the nuanced values of public trust (Klass, 2011: 1021).

Through the interaction of international economic and political perspectives, different public policies can be transferred across different periods. However, within the spectrum of liberalism-statism, neo-liberalism, ultra-liberalism, and ultra-protectionism, it may be beneficial to seek a balance that serves the public good. For instance, philosophical and policy implementation outcomes such as equitable income distribution and fair oversight of the cost burden of national development can impact citizens’ welfare. A study (Yılmaz and Bahçe, 2024) examined the effects of functional income distribution and fiscal policy on economic growth in Turkey in the context of labor and capital tax burdens, public spending, and public-private partnership investments, and found a tendency toward profit-oriented motives in the private sector. It was determined that differences in the philosophy of public service delivery through various channels did not lead to a change in the domestic demand regime; rather, it remained wage-oriented and profit-driven due to its sensitivity to labor costs in net exports. In

such an environment, the pursuit of social benefit may require greater attention to priorities such as employment, income, green investment, and a healthy environment (Yılmaz and Bahçe 2024).

On the other hand, within the context of debates on politics, ethics, and value philosophy, there are views suggesting that the concept of public interest corresponds to a regulatory framework aligned with the executive power of public administration, deriving its strength from its ambiguity, and that drawing it into ethical debate is impossible within the modern separation of powers system (Sümer 2014). Contrary to common belief, the notion of public interest is concluded to be less a response to ethical necessity and more a construct of political culture. Therefore, the question is sometimes raised: could the transition to renewable energy be not only a budgetary and planning issue but also a political choice?

Referring to European law and specifically examining the transformation of the concept of “public interest” in German energy law, Thierjung emphasizes that—especially after the Russia-Ukraine War—this concept has been redefined beyond climate policy to include strategic concerns such as energy security and political stability (Thierjung, 2023, p.169). Public interest is now viewed as a tool of security policy that guarantees the supply of safe and affordable energy. Renewable energy investments have become the concrete objective of public interest in the transformation of the energy system. In post-war Europe, particularly in Germany, newly enacted energy laws are legitimized as regulations serving the public interest. The concept of “public interest” is not a fixed standard; it is defined as a value-based decision shaped by the principle of majority among stakeholders in the decision-making process. Therefore, rather than an independent notion of “state interest,” there exists a variable concept of value shaped by public opinion. The definition of this concept is of vital importance for political movements (Thierjung, 2023, p.172).

For the sake of public interest, smart city governance and e-planning, artificial intelligence, citizen e-participation, social dimensions, virtual economy and nomadic workforce, digital platform cities and sharing economy, the liberation of smart cities from capitulation, a pluralistic and just future, and education in urban planning and planning ethics are essential (Urban e-Planning, 2025). To serve the public interest effectively, efficiently, and with dynamic balance, the development of centralized and local public administrative systems must be sustained. The continuation of these developments will also positively impact the quality of urban life (İnan, Ö., 2018; Yakin İnan, Ö., & Özdemir Sönmez, N., 2019; Özden, E., & Yücel Batmaz, N., 2022).

Globalization, social change, democracy, urbanization, and technology may have increased citizens’ demands. Concepts such as the participation ladder, conditions, legitimacy, and citizen panels may influence the search for new models. Public administration that prioritizes societal benefit can guide market conditions within legal boundaries, influencing public regulations, urban development, and the memory of civilization. In the pursuit of public interest, some studies argue that instead of regulation, the process of “deregulation” driven by external and side effects may positively contribute to growth (Öktem, 2025: 55).

2.2. Public Interest: Conceptual Framework

Although there is no objective definition of public interest, the concept varies according to time and place (Gül, 2014: 536). Public interest is a concept whose boundaries cannot be clearly defined and which changes according to the evolving needs of society. Therefore, it is difficult to establish a universally valid definition. Public interest can be assessed more effectively through its outcomes (Tombaloğlu, 2014: 363). In the literature, public interest is examined from various dimensions and encompasses economic, legal, social, and environmental factors aimed at enhancing societal welfare. Each discipline evaluates public interest from its own perspective, yet the ultimate goal remains to improve the overall quality of life and well-being of society.

Following the French Revolution (1789), the concept of public interest (common good of public / l’*intérêt général*) replaced the notion of the common good. In England, it has been recognized as “public interest” (Gül, 2014: 536). Public or societal interest should be understood not as the interest of the state or public sector, but as the interest of the people. In English, adjectives such as “public” or “publique” are used to refer not to official authorities or the state, but to the people and society (Keleş, 2000: 9).

The concept of public interest is one “whose essence or content is not predetermined, yet is recognized through its form.” A formal definition of public interest can be briefly understood as the assumption that laws are intended to serve the public interest. “It is presumed that every law enacted by the legislative body aims at

public interest. This presumption is also utilized by the administration. Accordingly, every administrative action is considered to be in the public interest unless proven otherwise” (Akıllıoğlu, 1991: 3).

In the Constitution of the Republic of Türkiye, the concept of public interest is frequently used in relation to topics such as the right to property, the right to work, the right to education and learning; as well as in matters of zoning, procurement, expropriation, use of law enforcement, administrative personnel regime (appointments, promotions, etc.), management of public assets and transactions involving these assets, administrative contracts, the supervisory authority of the administration, discretionary powers, and even administrative judicial procedures (Gül, 2014: 548). In this context, the third subsection of the “Social and Economic Rights and Duties” section under “Fundamental Rights and Duties” is titled “Public Interest.” Its subheadings include: Utilization of the Shores (Article 43), Land Ownership (Article 44), Protection of Agriculture, Animal Husbandry, and Workers in These Sectors (Article 45), Expropriation (Article 46), and finally, Nationalization (Article 47). Through this specific constitutional regulation, public interest is addressed not only in its formal aspect but also in terms of its substantive content (Akıllıoğlu, 1991: 4).

The concept of public interest has both broad and narrow meanings. In its broad sense, public interest carries political and ideological dimensions. Within this framework, public interest is linked to the fundamental political and social principles upon which constitutions are based. Therefore, it is more appropriate to refer to the broad meaning of public interest as societal interest. This is also the understanding reflected in the Constitution of the Republic of Türkiye. For example, in Article 43, which regulates the use of coastal areas, interpreting the term “public interest” in the heading as societal benefit is more accurate. While the authority to determine public interest in the narrow sense is generally granted to the executive branch, the responsibility to define societal interest in the broader sense is typically assigned to the legislative body (Keleş, 2000: 2).

The concept of public interest has been defined by the Turkish Constitutional Court as “ensuring the peace and welfare of the individual and society.” In constitutional jurisprudence and academic circles, the term is frequently expressed as “public benefit.” “The concept of public interest is an element that also grants discretionary power to state institutions” (Gül, 2014: 536).

In cases of conflict involving public interest, the Council of State has introduced the concept of “overriding public interest” in its rulings (Gül, 2014: 541). This concept becomes prominent in dilemmas between industrialization and urbanization activities that may negatively impact environmental values, and public investments such as energy, transportation, tourism, and housing versus efforts to protect the environment. In this context, the notion of overriding public interest arises from the tension between economic and social development goals pursued through investments and the aim of environmental protection. While public administration tends to interpret overriding public interest in terms of economic benefits and gains, the judiciary emphasizes the protection of natural resources and the environment (Mengi, 2018).

The Council of State, as the highest authority in judicial review, has adopted public interest as the fundamental criterion in its decisions, based on the understanding that all administrative actions must have public interest as their common and definitive objective. In this regard, the use of terms such as “societal interest, state interest, national interest, local interest, administrative interest, overriding public interest, and dominant public interest” provides concrete evidence of the evolving nature of the concept of public interest (Gül, 2014: 548). Having examined the conceptual framework of public interest, the relationship between renewable energy and public interest is then explored through examples from various countries.

3. COUNTRY CASES FOR PUBLIC INTEREST IN RENEWABLE ENERGY

To briefly consider concrete examples from other countries, the link between a clean environment and public health can once again be recalled. A study conducted in Southeast Asia examining the potential correlation between public health expenditures, logistics performance, renewable energy, and ecological sustainability (Sar et al., 2020) found that the use of renewable energy in logistics operations improves environmental and economic performance while reducing emissions. Thus, it is shown that increased environmental sustainability can enhance human health and economic growth. Conversely, rising public health expenditures combined with poor environmental performance, low efficiency, and reduced labor productivity may constrain economic growth and slow down economic activity. Additionally, the use of renewable energy in logistics can enhance a country’s image, attract direct foreign investment, and provide better export opportunities in environmentally

friendly countries that prioritize sustainable economic growth. In this regard, improved planning by public administration should be considered.

In an example from Northwestern Italy, a renewable energy community engaged in capital investment, with an independent company acquiring a stake and acting as a technology partner in management. The company shared revenues with the community, and both costs and profits were distributed collaboratively. The initiative demonstrated positive economic and environmental performance, with a return on investment of 11% and a 45% reduction in emissions, making it a compelling case (Cielo et al., 2020).

In South Korea, as a public policy measure against energy poverty, solar panels were installed on public rental housing. While the initiative aimed to reduce electricity bills and was publicly funded for tenants—who initially expressed satisfaction, the actual reduction in energy bills and system capacity led to a decline in satisfaction levels. The need for post-installation education, energy consumption feedback, and smart technologies was identified (Lee et al., 2020).

Different countries may face common challenges in the energy transition, and the alignment of society, technology, and public policy is considered crucial (Vanegas-Cantarero, 2020). In Global South countries, social initiatives are highlighted as shaping planning and decision-making processes. It is shown that social justice and democracy lie at the core of the transition. A rapid transition framework is proposed for developing countries. For expectations of economic development, social inclusion, and environmental sustainability, it is recommended that sustainable and renewable energy systems—based on assumptions of energy efficiency, affordability, reliability, and independence—be adapted and implemented as commercial products. In energy planning and regulation, redefining citizen participation and its demand, restructuring democratic institutions, and ensuring transparency, accountability, and trust-enhancing oversight are necessary.

Public opposition to renewable energy facilities and lack of public investment interest remain key barriers to sectoral development in the UK and some European countries (West et al., 2020). Although research examining public attitudes is increasing, viewing the public and public opinion as a homogeneous whole may be insufficient. A study adopting the framework of cultural theory has addressed individual views and behaviors, discussing how better public support and participation can be achieved by incorporating economic incentives, climate change awareness, and the relationship of renewable energies to overall energy behavior and landscape aesthetics.

Social acceptance can pose a significant barrier to the implementation of renewable energy systems. Although there is general support, low levels of local acceptance have been found to hinder project development. A study examining 25 case examples highlights the social motives and obstacles involved (Segreto et al., 2020). Through interviews with local residents, stakeholders, and experts, strategies are proposed to limit potential public opposition and enhance the development of renewable energy. After briefly evaluating the relationship between renewable energy and public interest through country examples, the study proceeds to examine Türkiye's core legislation and development plans related to renewable energy.

4. CORE LEGISLATION ON RENEWABLE ENERGY IN TÜRKİYE

In Türkiye, the initiative to promote electricity generation from renewable energy sources began with the enactment of Law No. 5346 on the Utilization of Renewable Energy Sources for the Purpose of Electricity Generation. Known as the Renewable Energy Law (YEK), it came into force in 2005 and represents the first legal regulation concerning Türkiye's renewable energy policy (Berksoy & Akdoğan, 2018: 24). According to YEK, production facilities based on renewable energy sources are defined as: "Facilities utilizing wind, solar, geothermal, biomass, gas derived from biomass (including landfill gas), wave, current energy, and tidal energy, as well as hydroelectric power plants of the canal or river type or those with a reservoir area of less than fifteen square kilometers, or pumped-storage hydroelectric facilities" (Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources, 2024: 9386).

Figure 1. Renewable Energy in Turkey: Laws, Regulations, Plans, and International Agreements

Kaynak: Berksoy & Akdoğan, 2018:23, İklim Değişikliği Azaltım Stratejisi ve Eylem Planı, 2024: 46-49, www.resmigazete.gov.tr/eskiler.

The laws, regulations, and plans presented in Figure 1 constitute the legal framework of Türkiye's renewable energy policy. The figure also incorporates the international agreements that Türkiye has signed. With the enactment of the Renewable Energy Law (YEK) in 2005, a legal foundation was established for investors in the field of renewable energy. This law enabled the implementation of the feed-in tariff (FiT) incentive mechanism. It also introduced support measures for land use aimed at renewable energy production (Berksoy & Akdoğan, 2018:24). Energy Efficiency Law No. 5627, published in 2007, extended the duration of the FiT mechanism under Law No. 5346 and increased the support rate for land use. Subsequently, Law No. 6094, enacted in 2010, introduced differentiated FiT applications based on energy source and launched a new incentive mechanism called the domestic contribution bonus (Berksoy & Akdoğan, 2018:24). The updated version of the Electricity Market Law No. 6446, which came into force in 2013, includes exemptions from license fees, stamp duty, corporate tax, and value-added tax. The Renewable Energy Resource Zones (YEKA) Regulation, published in 2016, implemented an auction-based incentive mechanism (Berksoy & Akdoğan, 2018:24). The National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (2017–2023) aimed to reduce Turkey's primary energy consumption by 14% compared to current levels across various sectors such as buildings and services, energy and heating, transportation, industry and technology, agriculture, and cross-cutting areas (IEA: 2021). Unlicensed electricity generation activities were regulated by the 2019 Regulation on Unlicensed Electricity Generation, which promotes small-scale renewable energy projects.

According to the Presidential Decree, under Law No. 5627 on Energy Efficiency dated August 16, 2019, public buildings with appointed energy managers were expected to achieve a 15% energy savings by 2023, aiming to use public resources efficiently and reduce energy costs (IEA, 2021). This target was raised to 30% by 2030 through the Presidential Circular dated November 4, 2023 (No. 2023/15) (Directorate for EU Affairs, 2024). The Regulation on Renewable Energy Resource Guarantee Certificate in the Electricity Market was published in the Official Gazette on November 14, 2020, and entered into force. The purpose of this regulation is to promote

the use of renewable energy sources in electricity generation and consumption, and to support environmental protection. In line with this goal, the regulation establishes a renewable energy source guarantee system that enables the tracking, verification, and disclosure of the amount or proportion of electricity supplied to consumers that is generated from renewable sources by licensed legal entities and allows consumers to procure certified electricity generated from renewable energy sources (Official Gazette, 2020).

In 2021, Türkiye ratified the Paris Climate Agreement, committing to reducing fossil fuel use and increasing renewable energy sources. The National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (2024–2030) aims to reduce energy consumption by 16% and achieve a reduction of 100 million tons of emissions by 2030. These laws and regulations demonstrate Turkey’s determination to expand renewable energy sources and promote energy efficiency (Energy Efficiency 2030 Strategy and II. National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, 2024). Türkiye signed the Paris Agreement on April 22, 2016, ratified it on October 6, 2021, and enacted it on November 10, 2021. The country has also announced its goal to become carbon neutral by 2053 (Ministry of Trade, 2024).

According to Türkiye’s National Energy Plan (2022), primary energy consumption is projected to reach 205.3 million tons of oil equivalent (Mtoe) and electricity consumption 510.4 terawatt-hours (TWh) by 2035. The share of electricity in final energy consumption is expected to rise to 24.9%, while energy intensity is targeted to be reduced by 35.3%. Installed electricity capacity will reach 189.7 gigawatts (GW), including 52.9 GW from solar, 29.6 GW from wind, and 7.2 GW from nuclear energy. Additionally, an extra 96.9 GW of installed capacity is targeted. Renewable energy will account for 54.7% of total electricity generation and 64.7% of installed capacity (Climate Change Mitigation Strategy and Action Plan, 2024:49).

The Action Plan included in the Energy Efficiency 2030 Strategy Document is organized into seven categories: “industry and technology, buildings and services, energy, transportation, agriculture, cross-cutting issues, start-ups and digitalization.” It aims to reduce energy consumption by 16% and contribute to a reduction of 100 million tons of emissions by the year 2030.

The key priorities outlined in the plan are as follows:

- Expanding the use of renewable energy
- Utilizing nuclear energy and natural gas as bridge fuel
- Discovering hydrocarbon resources and converting them into economic value
- Strengthening the energy infrastructure in line with transformation needs
- Investing in hydrogen, critical minerals, energy storage, and digitalization technologies
- Promoting and expanding domestic production in all areas of energy (II. National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, 2024).

The European Union plans to increase hydrogen’s share in Europe’s energy consumption to 13–14% by 2050. According to the report by Türkiye’s Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources (ETKB), Türkiye—being the EU’s sixth-largest trading partner and a significant global actor in renewable energy—should develop a clear national strategy on hydrogen to align with these goals. By doing so, Türkiye can enhance its technological capabilities and strengthen its global competitiveness (ETKB, 2023:6). The report, prepared in light of Türkiye’s hydrogen potential, sets a target to reduce the cost of green hydrogen production to below USD 2.4/kgH by 2035, and further down to USD 1.2/kgH by 2053. It also plans to increase installed electrolyzer capacity to 2 GW by 2030, 5 GW by 2035, and 70 GW by 2053. Türkiye’s strong renewable energy potential and strategic location will enable the domestically produced hydrogen—through R&D efforts—to be used both within the country and exported abroad (ETKB, 2023:1).

5. LINK TO SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT MANAGEMENT

The report titled “Our Common Future,” published in 1987 by the United Nations World Commission on Environment and Development and also known as the Brundtland Report, broadened the concept of sustainable development and contributed to its global recognition (Al, 2019:114). This concept emphasizes not only the environmental and economic dimensions of economic development but also the importance of a strong governance structure (Göçoğlu, Düzsöz & Demirkol, 2025).

The implementation of sustainable development becomes more meaningful through the concept of “development management” as defined by Edward W. Weidner. According to Weidner, development management is a dynamic administrative structure that drives socio-economic and politico-economic changes within society (Chandra, 2020). This concept provides an instrumental framework for public administration in defining, reinforcing, and implementing national goals in developing countries. Development management encompasses the preparation, organization, and execution of large-scale action programs, thereby enhancing administrative competence. It is a long-term process which requires a tough business-like approach, drawing on observations made over a number of years of working with various organizations, “commandments” for effective management development could be suggested (Margerison 1988).

Development management focuses on creating new organizational structures that enable an institution to effectively cope with change. Coordinating operations and development is a vital function of general management. As development management expands, the responsibilities of general management will become more complex and demanding, requiring a more careful and deliberate approach (Morris, 1971).

It can be defined not only as the management of development but also as the development of management itself, referring to the continuous improvement and renewal of administrative processes (Chandra, 2020). In support of pro-environmental climate in organizations, it has been indicated that “Green Inclusive Leadership positively influences Green Organizational Citizenship Behavior both directly and indirectly through the mediating roles of Happiness at Work and Self-Efficacy... Happiness at Work and Self-Efficacy sequentially enhance the relationship between Green Inclusive Leadership and Organizational Citizenship Behavior”, promoting employee well-being and self-confidence, which in turn fosters pro-environmental behaviors within organizations (Barik, Gupta, Kumari, Kumar 2025).

In Türkiye, a connection can be established between development plans, sustainable development, and development management. Since the early years of the Republic, development plans have been prioritized, and the sustainable development approach has been supported through economic, social, and environmental goals.

6. RENEWABLE ENERGY AND DEVELOPMENT PLANS IN TÜRKİYE

This section examines renewable energy topics in development plans between 2014 and 2024. The Tenth Development Plan projects a significant global increase in production levels from hydroelectric and other renewable energy power plants and anticipates that investments in these energy sources will reach levels comparable to the expenditures for exploration, procurement, and distribution of fossil fuels (Tenth Development Plan, 2014–2018: 14). Additionally, the plan sets a target to commission an additional 10,000 MW of hydroelectric capacity during this period. It also expects that publicly managed hydroelectric projects will reach completion, and that the share of public investment in the energy sector will decline due to privatizations (Tenth Development Plan, 2014–2018: 174, 82).

Following Türkiye’s signing of the Paris Agreement on April 22, 2016, the Eleventh Development Plan (2019–2023) addressed climate change mitigation through topics such as greenhouse gas emissions, air pollution, industrial chemicals, biodiversity, and environmental noise. Policies were planned to minimize the harmful effects of these environmental impacts (Tüysüz & Öncel, 2022: 652).

According to the Eleventh Development Plan (2019–2023: 112):

- Electricity generation from renewable energy sources will be increased.
- Necessary planning and investments will be made to ensure the safe integration of renewable energy production into the grid.
- Renewable energy sources will be effectively utilized in electricity generation through models similar to YEKA.
- Renewable energy production facilities will be safely integrated into the grid, and technical assistance projects will be implemented to support this process.
- To reduce the load of renewable energy production on the grid, pumped-storage hydroelectric power plants and energy storage systems will be established.

- Rehabilitation works will be carried out for Afşin-B Thermal Power Plant, Keban, Karakaya, and Hirfanlı Hydroelectric Power Plants.
- Nuclear Power Plants (NPPs) will be added to the electricity generation portfolio.
- Efforts will continue to increase the share of nuclear energy in electricity generation, and institutional capacity will be developed.
- In 2023, the construction of the first unit of Akkuyu NPP will be completed and electricity production will begin.
- In addition to Akkuyu NPP, efforts will continue for the establishment of two more nuclear power plants.
- The spread of energy-producing buildings will be promoted.
- Incentives will be provided to improve energy efficiency in existing buildings.
- A “National Green Building Certification System” will be established.
- Unlicensed solar and wind power plant applications will be expanded to meet electricity demand.
- The “Energy Efficiency Project for Public Buildings” will be implemented.

The primary objective of the 12th Development Plan is to ensure the uninterrupted, high-quality, sustainable, secure, and economical supply of energy, to diversify energy sources, and to achieve the net-zero emissions target by 2053. This plan aims to enhance energy self-sufficiency through the effective use of domestic and renewable energy resources, utilize nuclear technology in electricity generation, improve energy efficiency, promote domestic production in energy technologies, and integrate new technologies into the system. It also seeks to strengthen Türkiye’s strategic role in international energy trade (Climate Change Mitigation Strategy and Action Plan, 2024: 47).

In conclusion, the emphasis on sustainable energy in Türkiye’s development plans—prepared with a development management approach—demonstrates public benefit across various dimensions, based on environmental protection, economic growth, and social welfare. These plans offer both direct and indirect benefits to the public and contribute to the realization of long-term sustainable development goals.

7. NET ZERO EMISSIONS TARGET FOR 2053

Türkiye aims to achieve net-zero emissions by 2053, in line with the Paris Climate Agreement. In this context, the Climate Law was published in the Official Gazette on July 9, 2025, and entered into force on the same day. With this law, Türkiye has established a legal foundation for its environmental and climate policies in line with its low-carbon development goals. Embedding climate policies within a legal framework is essential for safeguarding the public interest. In this process, Türkiye aims to reduce emissions by decreasing the use of fossil fuels and increasing the share of renewable energy sources (T.C. Resmî Gazete, 2025).

Although the legal and administrative infrastructure for coal (as national source) phase-out in Türkiye is still under consideration, and more strong transformation process into clean energy is needed; the share of renewable energy among the energy sources used for electricity generation in the country continues to increase year by year. According to data from the Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources (ETKB), Türkiye ranked 11th globally in 2023 with an installed renewable energy capacity of 58,462 MW. As of 2024, the distribution of electricity generation by source is as follows: 35.2% coal, 18.9% natural gas, 21.5% hydro, 10.5% wind, 7.5% solar, 3.2% geothermal, and 3.2% other sources (ETKB, 2024). By the end of February 2025, the distribution of installed capacity by source was reported as: 27.5% hydro, 21% natural gas, 18.7% coal, 11.2% wind, 17.8% solar, 1.5% geothermal, and 2.3% other sources (ETKB, 2024).

Table 1. Share of Energy Sources in Electricity Generation

	2025	2030	2035
Thermal Energy	51.7%	44.5%	34.2%
Nuclear Energy	4.9%	8.2%	11.1%
Hydroelectric Energy	21.5%	19.4%	17.3%
Wind Energy	10.1%	11.9%	17.7%
Solar Energy	7.4%	11.5%	16.5%
Other (Geothermal and biomass)	4.4%	4.5%	3.2%
Total	100%	100%	100%

Source: Türkiye Ulusal Enerji Planı, 2022: 35.

In order to achieve the net-zero emissions target by 2053, it is necessary to reduce the use of fossil fuels in electricity generation and replace them with renewable energy sources. The electricity system will undergo a transformation, increasing the share of renewables. While approximately 40% of electricity generation came from renewable sources in 2020, this share is projected to reach 90% (899 TWh) by 2053. Solar and wind energy will become the dominant energy sources by 2053. Technologies such as hydrogen and biogas-powered plants, battery energy storage, pumped-storage hydroelectric systems, and demand-side participation will provide flexibility to the electricity system (Shura Energy Transition Center, 2023: 97–98).

According to *Shura's Net Zero 2053* scenario, the use of e-fuels in the gas grid will begin in 2035, and the carbon footprint will be eliminated by 2055 (Shura, 2023: 53). The transition to e-fuel use in industry will also start in 2035, with a phased reduction of fossil fuel use expected to be completed by 2050. In this context, Türkiye's natural gas pipeline infrastructure will undergo transformation, gradually shifting toward e-fuel usage (Shura, 2023: 19). The absence of swift action is expected to increase cumulative greenhouse gas emissions by keeping coal and lignite power plants in the system beyond 2035. This would hinder the transition to renewable energy and make it more difficult for Türkiye to achieve its net zero emissions target, while also increasing implementation risks (Shura, 2023: 100).

8. RECOMMENDATION FOR LOCAL GOVERNMENTS ON RENEWABLE ENERGY

As emphasized by Francesco La Camera, Director-General of the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), which had 170 members as of 2024 (169 countries and the EU), the rapid growth of renewable energy sources continues year after year. This growth demonstrates that these energy sources are not only environmentally beneficial but also economically viable and scalable. Renewable energy technologies such as solar and wind are playing a significant role in the global energy system, especially as costs decline. While the sector continues to break records with its expansion rates, it also faces critical challenges. In some regions, issues such as lack of infrastructure, insufficient financial resources, and political instability can slow the transition to renewable energy. Achieving international sustainability and climate goals by 2030 will require cooperation and effort to overcome these challenges (IRENA, 2025). Aligning global initiatives led by international organizations that promote the adoption and use of renewable energy—such as IRENA, the International Energy Agency, the World Energy Council, and the Association of Mediterranean Energy Regulators—with local projects can accelerate progress toward renewable energy targets. Local governments, being the closest administrative level to communities' individual needs, play a critical role in raising public awareness, supporting innovative projects, and developing infrastructure. This alignment can increase the success rate of renewable energy projects by taking into account region-specific requirements and obstacles. In this context, both global cooperation and effective evaluation of local dynamics will play a key role in developing sustainable solutions for the energy transition (Usta & Atar, 2025: 26).

According to a survey, the two most important steps that local governments in Türkiye should take against the climate crisis are investing in renewable energy and developing infrastructure projects; 36% of respondents identified renewable energy investments, while another 36% highlighted strengthening infrastructure against

floods and heavy rainfall as top priorities for municipalities. In the survey, 55% of the public stated that the greatest responsibility for addressing the climate crisis lies with the government or the president. This was followed by 22% who pointed to local governments/municipalities, 13% to civil society organizations, 7% to the private sector/industry, and 4% to political parties (Temizenerji.org, 2024-b).

In a briefing note presented to mayoral candidates by civil society organizations working on climate and urban issues, it was emphasized that the savings generated from the energy transition would improve living standards in cities, and concrete steps that municipalities can take swiftly were outlined (Temizenerji.org, 2024-c). Enhancing energy efficiency and transitioning to renewable energy sources such as solar and wind will play a critical role in addressing global energy crises and high energy costs. The advantages of this transition are significant both for society and public welfare. Key advantages of the energy transition include: redirecting savings toward enhancing public services and advancing social programs, decreasing reliance on fossil fuels, it will expand regional employment opportunities, it will protect the environment and climate, it will ensure energy security during disasters, it will enable citizens to contribute to the energy transition (Temizenerji.org, 2024-c).

To achieve these benefits, civil society organizations have proposed a set of policy recommendations. The first of these is that local governments should prioritize energy transition in their action plans. Through their action plans (such as sustainable energy and/or climate change action plans), local governments should take into account the needs of disadvantaged groups and ensure their support. At the same time, they should promote the increased use of renewable energy sources and develop necessary projects to enhance energy efficiency to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. (Temizenerji.org, 2024-c).

Additionally, citizen complaint and redress mechanisms would be an important starting point for protecting the public interest. (Auditor General of Canada, 1999). Local governments should become key actors in the energy transition by assuming the role of “Energy Solution Hubs.” In this context, units called “Energy Solution Desks” should be established within local administrations to lead awareness-raising activities related to energy. These units should offer training sessions for the public and local businesses on how to read electricity bills accurately and provide information on energy efficiency and savings methods. (Temizenerji.org, 2024-c). Public consultation and feedback mechanisms play a vital role in safeguarding the public interest (Auditor General of Canada, 1999). Furthermore, during the transition to renewable energy systems, guidance and support should be provided to residents and businesses to help them contribute to this transformation process. (Temizenerji.org, 2024-c).

Another policy recommendation is to support and promote the use of renewable energy in public buildings. Local governments should invest in meeting the energy needs of public buildings through renewable sources. Türkiye’s rooftops offer a solar energy potential of 120 GW, which corresponds to 45% of the country’s total electricity consumption in 2022. Municipalities can benefit from this potential by installing solar panels on the rooftops of buildings such as hospitals, schools, sports facilities, neighborhood markets, marriage halls, social centers, and parking lots (Temizenerji.org, 2024-c). A pioneering example of this policy recommendation is the solar energy system (SES) installed at the Main Service Building of Tepebaşı Municipality. This system meets approximately 23% of the building’s electricity needs, helping to reduce energy costs and contributing to environmental sustainability. (Eskişehir Tepebaşı Belediyesi, 2022).

Moreover, it is crucial for local governments to streamline processes and reduce bureaucracy to enhance the effectiveness of renewable energy projects. In this regard, they should simplify and make permit procedures more accessible to ensure rapid implementation of projects. Additionally, training programs should be organized to improve the knowledge and competencies of staff involved in these processes, and capacity-building activities should be prioritized (Temizenerji.org, 2024-c).

Another key policy recommendation is for local governments to take steps to expand the use of solar energy in buildings within their jurisdiction. Accordingly, all new buildings should be designed and constructed to accommodate rooftop solar energy systems. At the same time, during renovation processes of existing buildings, the installation of rooftop solar systems should be encouraged. These incentives should aim to enhance sustainability in energy production and promote the efficient use of local energy resources. In the long term, it is planned that these practices will gradually become mandatory, leading to widespread adoption of solar energy across the entire city (Temizenerji.org, 2024-c).

The latest policy recommendation communicated to local governments is the promotion of vocational training and (green) employment. Local administrations should organize training programs in the fields of renewable energy and energy efficiency to cultivate experts not only in technical roles but also in areas such as bureaucracy and finance (Temizenerji.org, 2024-c).

In this context, local governments must organize comprehensive training programs in key areas such as renewable energy and energy efficiency. These programs should not only aim to train qualified personnel for technically specialized positions but also contribute to the development of experts with competencies in bureaucracy, project management, and finance. By doing so, the processes related to the energy transition can be accelerated, and employment opportunities can be expanded, allowing broader segments of society to benefit from this transformation. If these steps are implemented swiftly, the realization of renewable energy projects will also generate significant public benefit. (Temizenerji.org, 2024-c).

9. CONCLUDING REMARKS: “MASTER TAILOR CAN SEW A ROOMY SHIRT FROM A NARROW PIECE OF FABRIC”

The pessimism surrounding the depletion of fossil fuels (possibly within 20 years) has been reiterated for years. While the proposition of resource scarcity can be debated economically, in the context of energy, it is worth analyzing whether it could serve as a solution for countries seeking a way out of constrained development cycles.

If renewable energy offers a socially beneficial model, it deserves thorough examination. Countries, technologies, and preferences should be assessed, and a collaborative model involving cooperatives, companies, public administration, civil society, and local government institutions should be developed and presented for public benefit. This effort merits attention and commitment for the sake of public value.

A key question arises: if public benefit exists, why is it not sufficiently developed and implemented? At the very least, the theoretical reservations surrounding the diffusion of innovation and innovativeness can be recalled. Moreover, innovation does not occur instantly or spontaneously (Öktem 2010: 42, citing Streib & Willoughby, 2005:83). In public administration, institutional leadership, collaboration, effective communication, and co-innovation development are essential. Factors such as literacy on the subject, access, usability, and financial incentives should be considered. In other words, renewable energy innovation should embody the meaning of “public good, public preference, public demand, and public will.”

Individuals cannot determine how much they consume or the unit cost. Technically, every individual in society should be on equal footing; it should be distributed nationwide and provide collective benefit, either financially or in-kind. One citizen’s use should not hinder another’s, and there must be sufficient capacity. The outcome should satisfy the entire society. The ultimate goal must be to maximize public welfare and benefit. Public service, public law, or universal service should be delivered equally and uninterruptedly to every citizen (Öktem 2010: 47, citing Koray, 2005:86–90).

Ultimately, in the countries examined and specifically in Türkiye, renewable energy management from the perspective of public benefit is a strategic planning and implementation process carried out for economic, social, and environmental security of the nation’s future. Since the concept of public benefit is generally evaluated by its outcomes (Tombaloğlu, 2014:363), the output of renewable energy management is also public benefit. Through centrally and locally prepared development plans and implementations, Türkiye can achieve economic returns, environmental and social benefits, and technological progress, while also contributing to public welfare and ensuring long-term societal prosperity through sustainable development goals.

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